

Supplementary Proof of Collision-Freeness for MCCA Formulation

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I. PROBLEM

Consider the following MCCA QP formulation presented in our paper:

$$\min \alpha_1 \|\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{v}^{\text{pref}}\|_2^2 + \alpha_2 \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}} \delta_i^2 + \alpha_3 \sum_{j \in \mathcal{R}} \delta_j^2 + \alpha_4 \sum_{k \in \mathcal{M}} \delta_k^2 \quad (1)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \det(\mathbf{B}) \leq \delta_\zeta, \zeta \in \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{R} \cup \mathcal{M}, \delta_\zeta \geq 0 \quad (1a)$$

$$\dot{\mathbf{q}} = \mathbf{S}(\mathbf{q}) \cdot \mathbf{r} \quad (1b)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{F} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{G} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\mathbf{q}} \\ \mathbf{r} \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{0}. \quad (1c)$$

where \mathcal{M} is the set of MCCA half-planes against all other robots, \mathcal{O} and \mathcal{R} are the set of ORCA half-planes against obstacles and all other robots, respectively. Constraint (1b) and (1c) incorporate nonholonomic kinematic constraints. Constraint (1a) describes the half-planes of permitted velocities for the current robot. Each of the half-plane is induced by a robot $\zeta \in \mathcal{R}$ or a static obstacle $\zeta \in \mathcal{O}$ or a MCCA half-plane $\zeta \in \mathcal{M}$.

For the constraints concerning ORCA half-planes, if a solution exists on condition that $\delta_\zeta = 0$, $\zeta \in \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{R}$, all the ORCA half-planes are satisfied and in such case it is proven in the ORCA paper that the velocity solved is collision-free. In our method, the constraints are not strict as δ_ζ may go beyond 0. If δ_ζ is positive, it is punished heavily in the objective function so that the violation of the ORCA half-planes is kept minimum. We then give proof that if the bounding circle radius of each robot is increased to a certain level, ORCA half-planes are not violated in terms of the real radius, thus collision-freeness is guaranteed. Our proof also shows that the increase can be marginal when the weights α_1 to α_4 are properly set.

In the ORCA paper if a solution satisfying all ORCA half-planes does not exist, which is possible in dense situations, collision-freeness can not be guaranteed and a velocity that causes the least violation of the half-planes is pursued. In this case, our method serves exactly the same purpose.

II. PROOF

Theorem 1: For each robot, if there exists a velocity satisfying all ORCA half-planes, the real velocity solved with (1) is collision-free if the bounding circle radius is enlarged

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by at least $2\tau v^{\max} \sqrt{\frac{2\alpha_1 + \alpha_4 n}{\min(\alpha_2, \alpha_3)}}$, where τ is the time horizon, n is the number of robots.

Proof: Given that there exists a velocity satisfying all ORCA half-planes, a solution to (1), $x' = (v'_x, v'_y, \delta'_{i_1}, \dots, \delta'_{i_o}, \delta'_{i_{o+1}}, \dots, \delta'_{i_{o+n}}, \delta'_{k_1}, \dots, \delta'_{k_n})$ exists, where $i_1, \dots, i_{o+n} \in \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{R}, k_1, \dots, k_n \in \mathcal{M}$, such that $\delta'_{i_1}, \dots, \delta'_{i_{o+n}} = 0$.

Let $f(x)$ denotes the objective function in (1) and $x^* = (v_x^*, v_y^*, \delta_{i_1}^*, \dots, \delta_{i_o}^*, \delta_{i_{o+1}}^*, \dots, \delta_{i_{o+n}}^*, \delta_{k_1}^*, \dots, \delta_{k_n}^*)$ denotes an optimal solution. $f(x^*) \leq f(x')$ leads to

$$\begin{aligned} & \alpha_1 (v_x^* - v_x^{\text{pref}})^2 + \alpha_1 (v_y^* - v_y^{\text{pref}})^2 \quad (2) \\ & + \alpha_2 \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}} (\delta_i^*)^2 + \alpha_3 \sum_{j \in \mathcal{R}} (\delta_j^*)^2 + \alpha_4 \sum_{k \in \mathcal{M}} (\delta_k^*)^2 \\ & < \\ & \alpha_1 (v'_x - v_x^{\text{pref}})^2 + \alpha_1 (v'_y - v_y^{\text{pref}})^2 \\ & + \alpha_2 \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O}} (\delta'_i)^2 + \alpha_3 \sum_{j \in \mathcal{R}} (\delta'_j)^2 + \alpha_4 \sum_{k \in \mathcal{M}} (\delta'_k)^2. \end{aligned}$$

Since $\delta'_{i_1}, \dots, \delta'_{i_{o+n}} = 0$, $\sum_{i \in \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{R}} (\delta'_i)^2 = 0$. We now rearrange the inequation and get

$$\begin{aligned} & \min(\alpha_2, \alpha_3) \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{R}} (\delta_i^*)^2 \\ & < \\ & \alpha_1 ((v'_x - v_x^{\text{pref}})^2 - (v_x^* - v_x^{\text{pref}})^2) \\ & + (v'_y - v_y^{\text{pref}})^2 - (v_y^* - v_y^{\text{pref}})^2 + \alpha_4 \sum_{k \in \mathcal{M}} ((\delta'_k)^2 - (\delta_k^*)^2). \quad (3) \end{aligned}$$

Further, $|v_x| \leq v^{\max}$, so that $|v'_x - v_x^{\text{pref}}|, |v_x^* - v_x^{\text{pref}}| \leq 2v^{\max}$ and

$$(v'_x - v_x^{\text{pref}})^2 - (v_x^* - v_x^{\text{pref}})^2 \leq 4(v^{\max})^2. \quad (4)$$

Similarly,

$$(v'_y - v_y^{\text{pref}})^2 - (v_y^* - v_y^{\text{pref}})^2 \leq 4(v^{\max})^2. \quad (5)$$

From the QP formulation, the MCCA constraints are effective iff $\det(\mathbf{B}) > 0$, and in this case the inequality can be reduced to equality, therefore $\delta_k = \det(\mathbf{B})$ when $\delta_k > 0$. With the definition of $\det(\mathbf{B})$ and the half-plane shown in Section IV, the distance between a velocity and a half-plane

violated can be derived as $\frac{d_y^{\zeta}(v_x - p_x) - d_x^{\zeta}(v_y - p_y)}{\sqrt{(d_x^{\zeta})^2 + (d_y^{\zeta})^2}}$. By definition of the half-plane the norm of its direction is scaled to 1, and the distance can be reduced to $d_y^{\zeta}(v_x - p_x) - d_x^{\zeta}(v_y - p_y)$, which is the value of $\det(\mathbf{B})$ and equals δ_k as mentioned above. From the formulation of the velocity obstacle and the half-plane, the distance is less than the norm of the relative velocity, therefore $\delta_k \leq 2v^{\max}$. Then we have $(\delta'_k)^2 - (\delta_k^*)^2 \leq 4(v^{\max})^2$. Therefore

$$\min(\alpha_2, \alpha_3) \sum_{i \in \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{R}} (\delta_i^*)^2 < 8\alpha_1(v^{\max})^2 + 4\alpha_4 n(v^{\max})^2. \quad (6)$$

Since $(\delta_i^*)^2 \geq 0$, we have

$$\min(\alpha_2, \alpha_3)(\delta_i^*)^2 < 8\alpha_1(v^{\max})^2 + 4\alpha_4 n(v^{\max})^2, i \in \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{R}, \quad (7)$$

which can be expressed as

$$\delta_i^* < 2v^{\max} \sqrt{\frac{2\alpha_1 + \alpha_4 n}{\min(\alpha_2, \alpha_3)}}, i \in \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{R}. \quad (8)$$

If the solved velocity violates any of the ORCA half-planes, the distance(or penetration) from the solved velocity to the violated half-planes is bounded by this inequation. Thus the new half-planes constraining the solved velocity can be viewed as the original ORCA half-planes translating a distance of $d = 2v^{\max} \sqrt{\frac{2\alpha_1 + \alpha_4 n}{\min(\alpha_2, \alpha_3)}}$. Therefore the boundary of the truncated cone of the velocity obstacle constructed with the enlarged radius should also keep a distance d from the boundary of the velocity obstacle constructed with the real radius, such that collision is avoided. To achieve this, in terms of collision avoidance against another robot, the radius of both the discs centered at $(p_B - p_A)$ and $(p_B - p_A)/\tau$ should increase at least $\frac{d}{2}$, thus the bounding circle radius should increase at least $\frac{\tau d}{2}$. In terms of collision avoidance against an obstacle line segment, the bound circle radius should increase at least τd . We can conclude that if the bounding circle radius is $2\tau v^{\max} \sqrt{\frac{2\alpha_1 + \alpha_4 n}{\min(\alpha_2, \alpha_3)}}$ larger than the real radius of each robot, then all ORCA half-planes are satisfied and collision-freeness is guaranteed.

Note that α_1 to α_4 is at our disposal, we can assign proper value to increase the radius only marginally while maintaining collision-freeness.